

AN X-BAND, 2.5 WATT CONTINUOUS WAVE DIELECTRIC RESONATOR OSCILLATOR FOR FUTURE MILITARY SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

A 9 GHz Dielectric Resonator Oscillator (DRO) generating a continuous wave (CW) power output of 2.5 watts at room temperature has been designed and fabricated by incorporating a high power GaAs FET amplifier and a Murata Erie dielectric resonator (DR) in a feedback loop oscillator configuration. The DC to RF conversion efficiency of this DRO is about 11%. The oscillator exhibited a frequency stability of less than 130 ppm over the temperature range of -50°C to $+50^{\circ}\text{C}$. Measured single-sideband phase noise levels were -105 dBc/Hz and -135 dBc/Hz at 10 kHz and 100 kHz carrier offset frequencies, respectively. The output power varied from $+35$ dBm (3.2 watts) at -50°C to $+33$ dBm (2 watt) at $+50^{\circ}\text{C}$. The DRO output power is then fed into a single-stage GaAs FET amplifier, resulting in a total power output of 6.5 watts at X-band. The overall efficiency of the 6.5 watt DRO unit is about 12%. The pulse power capability of the DRO unit was also investigated. The unit can deliver 10 watts of pulse power for a pulse duration of one microsecond or less.

INTRODUCTION

The high power, high efficiency, light weight, small size, temperature stable, DRO reported will aid in satisfying the frequency stability and the output power requirements of an Army man-portable radar transponder. The man-portable radar transponder is deployed by long-range Special Operation Forces (SOF) patrols for use as a forward air controller/strike aircraft rendezvous aid. When the transponder is interrogated by an incoming aircraft, it responds either at X- or Ku-band frequency.

The X-band, 6.5 watt DRO unit contains only two GaAs FET amplifiers. One of which is used in the oscillator circuit and the other one is

used for amplifying the DRO output signal. Circuits employing fewer active devices are very cost effective, easy to reproduce, and are more reliable because of less parts count. An overall block diagram of the high power DRO unit is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. DRO Unit Block Diagram

The peak power capability of the DRO unit was studied in detail for the transponder application. A minimum power output of 10 watts was measured over a wide temperature range. This power is needed to drive an output power stage that contain four 10 watt GaAs FET amplifiers in parallel to produce 25 watts of X-band peak power over the military temperature range. The 25 watt pulsed power, when fed into a microstrip patch antenna having 9 dB gain, will correspond to more than 200 watts of effective radiated power (ERP). The transponder range requirement of 100 kilometer is easily achievable with the stated propagating energy. Link equations were developed and solved to calculate the required transmit power. Some of the parameters used in the link equations are transponder and interrogator antenna gain, path loss, receiver sensitivity, multiple path loss, etc. The transponder transmitter power for X- and Ku-band were found to be 18 watts and 13 watts, respectively.

The sophisticated state-of-the-art power DRO discussed in this paper will provide enhanced system performance for the transponder, and can

be configured for use in future systems to meet advanced DoD requirements for smart munitions, EW survivable all-weather surveillance, and target acquisition systems. A Ku-band, high power DRO is still under construction. The goal is to produce twice the power at half the frequency and use a ISIS diode frequency doubler circuit to obtain a Ku-band signal.

OSCILLATOR DESIGN

The feedback loop oscillator is designed by combining a two-port GaAs FET amplifier with a two-port transmission-mode dielectric resonator. The amplifier and the DR enclosed in a metal cavity are treated separately. Dielectric resonator oscillators and acoustic resonator based oscillators designed this way have been shown to have excellent phase noise and frequency stability [1-5]. The residual phase noise of the oscillator's components should be evaluated to avoid overall phase noise degradation due to low quality/faulty RF components. The absolute phase noise of the oscillator, within the resonator's bandwidth, can be calculated by knowing the amplifier/resonator residual noise and the loaded Q of the resonator [6-7]. The resonator used in the oscillator design was procured from Murata Erie. It has a dielectric constant of 24.2 and a temperature coefficient of zero parts per million per degree centigrade. The dielectric resonator had an unloaded Q of 22,000 at X-band. The dimension of the resonator are 7.07 mm in diameter and 3.14 mm thick.

CAVITY DESIGN

The cavity dimensions are chosen such that the $TE_{01\delta}$ mode of the resonator is well separated from the cavity modes. The amount of coupling and the positioning of the DR in the cavity are very critical in obtaining an optimum performance. A spacer made of low dielectric constant material is used for mounting the DR inside the cavity. Improper mounting will degrade the loaded Q, and increase vibration sensitivity. The cavity design is shown in Figure 2.

The cavity is made of brass and is cylindrical in shape. The cavity mode in the absence of the resonator is analyzed using the cylindrical cavity resonant frequency formula. The calculated modes are then verified by network analysis measurements. Figure 3 shows the air filled cavity modes. These mode are identified as TE_{111} ,

Cross-Sectional View

Figure 2. Two Port Cavity Design

TM_{010} and TM_{011} operating at 8.765 GHz, 8.985 GHz and 10.415 GHz respectively. These modes were excited by a 50 ohm microstrip line, located at the bottom of the cavity. Figure 4 shows the mode spectra in the presence of the DR.

As expected, the cavity modes had shifted lower in frequency due to the presence of high dielectric constant material, (i.e. the DR). Figure 4 also shows the mode separation between the $TE_{01\delta}$ mode and the cavity modes.

The resonance frequency of the DR is tuned via fringing fields perturbations by a metallic screw. The cavity modes are also very sensitive to the tuning screw. Figure 5 illustrates the behavior of the cavity modes as the screw is plunged into the cavity from the top. The TM_{011} mode is extremely sensitive to the tuning screw and completely overlaps the $TE_{01\delta}$ mode at some tuning position. Figure 5 suggests that one has to be very careful with the tuning screw, carelessness could result in operating on an undesired cavity mode.

S₂₁ /M1 log MAG
 REF 0.0 dB
 10.0 dB/-15.989 dB

Figure 3. Cavity Modes Excited by Microstrip Line

S₂₁ /M1 log MAG
 REF 0.0 dB
 10.0 dB/-39.182 dB

Figure 5. Behavior of Cavity Modes as a Function of Tuning Screw

S₂₁ /M1 log MAG
 REF 0.0 dB
 10.0 dB/-42.346 dB

Figure 4. Cavity Modes and the TE₀₁₀ Mode of the DR

The result of loaded Q measurement is shown in Figure 6. A 3 dB bandwidth of 1.49984 MHz at a center frequency of 9.041GHz corresponds to a Q of 6,028. The insertion loss was about 4 dB. A loaded Q of 15,000 was measured with 20 dB

Figure 6. Measured 3 dB Bandwidth of the Resonator. Corresponding loaded Q is 6,028 with 4 dB insertion loss.

insertion loss. Three loop amplifiers would have been required to overcome this insertion loss.

AMPLIFIER DESIGN

The amplifier is designed with a commercially available, internally matched, Fujitsu FLM 8596-8C GaAs field effect transistor. The 1 dB gain compression point of the amplifier is about 8 watts. The amplifier has bandwidth of approximately 1 GHz with maximum gain at 9.041 GHz, which is the puck frequency. The residual phase noise of the high power GaAs FET amplifier was calculated to be -130dBc/Hz at 100 Hz offset frequency. Bias network and the tuning stubs were fabricated on a 10 mil thick RT 5880 duroid board. Tuning was needed to achieve maximum gain at the puck frequency. Design precautions were taken to avoid any bias circuit oscillation.

MEASURED RESULTS

The microstrip circuit board layout of the DRO is shown in Figure 7. The amplifier, the Cavity and the Wilkinson power divider were designed and tested individually for optimum performance.

Figure 7. Dielectric Resonator Stabilized Single-Stage Feedback-Loop Microstrip Circuit Board Layout

The DRO's output power, center frequency and the spectral purity was measured by a HP 8566B spectrum analyzer. The test setup and the measured data are shown in Figures 8 and 9, respectively. A 20 dB pad was used between the DRO output port and the spectrum analyzer. The output power is 33.9 dBm (2.5 watt). (12.90 dBm from the plot of Figure 8 + 20dB pad + 1dB cable loss =33.90 dBm). The oscillator has no spurious oscillation and the second harmonic power level is 35 dB below the carrier power level.

Figure 8. Power Output Measurement Test Setup

Figure 9. Measured DRO Output Power. (12.9 dBm+ 20 dB Pad+1 dB Cable loss=33.90 dBm)

The center frequency and the output power variation with temperature from -50°C to +50°C are given in Figures 10 and 11, respectively. The measurement started after stabilizing the environmental chamber at -50°C for 1 hour. The total frequency drift is less than 130 ppm and is well within the transponder specification. The frequency vs temperature characteristic was reinvestigated under low output power (20 dBm)

condition. The result of this measurement is shown in Figure 10. The highest frequency drift observed in this case is about 80 ppm. This is a factor of 1.6 improvement over the previous data. Non-linearities in the active device may be responsible for the additional degradation observed under high power condition. The output power varied from +35 dBm (3.2 watts) at -50°C to +33 dBm (2 watt s) at +50°C. The room temperature power is 33.9 dBm (2.5 watts).

Figure 10. Frequency vs Temperature Plot

Figure 11. High Power DRO Output Power vs Temperature Data

The absolute phase noise performance of the high power DRO was measured with a HP 3047A noise measurement system. The test setup is illustrated in the graph of Figure 12. The DRO test signal was downconverted to 151 MHz signal by mixing it with a low noise high overtone bulk acoustic resonator (HBAR) oscillator. The 151 MHz signal is then phase locked to an HP 8662A frequency synthesizer driven by an external 10 MHz VCXO. This arrangement was necessary due to a lack of a second source with VCO capability. The single sideband phase noise plot is shown in Figure 13. The synthesizer noise starts to show up at 100 kHz offset frequency. The spurs between 100 kHz and 1 MHz are due to mixer products. The spurs between 60 Hz and 1 kHz are due to AC line spurs.

Figure 12. Phase Noise Measurement Test Setup

Figure 13. Absolute Phase Noise of High Power DRO

Finally the output power was measured again after adding the single-stage amplifier at the output of the DRO. The measurement test setup is exactly the same as the one described in Figure 8. The result of this measurement is shown in Figure 14. The total output power is 38.2 dBm (6.5 watt).

Figure 14. Output Power Measured for the DRO Unit (17.2 dBm+21 dB Line loss=38.2 dBm)

CONCLUSIONS

A detailed study of a 2.5 watt, X-band DRO has been reported in this paper. The spectral purity and the frequency stability are considered excellent for such a high power DRO. The overall unit provides 6.5 watt CW output power at 9 GHz and has 11.82 % DC to RF conversion efficiency. The unit is small and draws 4.23 amp at 10 VDC. It can also be used for pulse power application.

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